

EFFECTS OF FLEXURAL BEHAVIOR AND DAMAGE PATTERN ON THE ACOUSTIC EMISSION

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ABSTRACT

The 18 lay-up sequences which have some relationships between them were tested in three points flexural test with acoustic emission (AE) control. The AE results were compared with the flexural behavior, the results by ultrasonic test and the microscopic observations. The various damage patterns induced by the different lay-up sequences and the ratios of the span to the thickness of the specimen have a strong influence on the AE results.

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials under flexural test experience complex damage mechanisms which can be introduced by tensile, compressive and shear stress components simultaneously. The damage mechanisms may include matrix cracking, fibre breakage, delamination and debonding of phases, etc. The lay-up sequences and the ratio of span to the thickness of specimen influence on the flexural behavior and then on the damage mechanism[1-6].

There are close relationships between the damage mechanisms and the AE results. In most AE studies, limited numbers of complex lay-up sequences were usually employed complicating the interpretation of AE observation. And the comparison between the AE observation and the results obtained by another methods was not generally given. Such comparison is beneficial for the proper use of AE control to distinguish different failure modes [7-14].

The aim of this work is to provide some guides for the AE control by correlating the AE results with the results obtained by another experiments. The events of AE and the distribution of peak amplitude of AE are mainly considered.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

The specimens were made by using carbon/epoxy prepreg p3052 from Toray industry with autoclave curing method. The carbon fibre volume fraction was about 0.6 for the cured laminates. The 8 plied specimen had a thickness of about 1 mm. The off-axis 8 plied specimens, $(0^\circ)_8$, $(15^\circ)_8$, $(30^\circ)_8$, $(45^\circ)_8$, $(60^\circ)_8$, $(75^\circ)_8$ and $(90^\circ)_8$ were prepared. They were designated as A,B,C,D,E,F and G. The structures of other 8 plied specimens were $(\pm 45^\circ)_{2S}$, $(90^\circ/0^\circ)_{2S}$, $(90^\circ/0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ)_S$, $(0^\circ/90^\circ/\pm 45^\circ)_S$ and $(0^\circ/90^\circ)_{2S}$. They were designated as H,I,J,K and L. The another structures of $(0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ)$, $(90^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ)$, $(0^\circ/90^\circ)_S$, $(90^\circ/0^\circ)_S$, $(0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ)_S$ and $(90^\circ/\pm 45^\circ)_S$ were also prepared.

Experimental Methods

The three points flexural tests were done by Instron 1122 at the crosshead speed of 2mm/min. The length and the width of specimen were always 80 and 20 mm, respectively. The ratios of span to the thickness of specimen were 40:1 and 16:1 for 8 plied specimens and maintained 40:1 for the specimens which had not 8 plies. Three specimens were used for each condition. The maximum stress was determined from the following relationship :

$$S_{\max} = 3PL / 2bd^2 \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where S_{\max} : maximum stress
P : maximum load
L : loading span
b : width of specimen
d : thickness of specimen

Acoustic emissions were monitored on an computer based AET Model 5000. The transducer was MAC 300L with a resonant frequency of 300KHz. The detected signals were passed through a band pass filter FL 25 with a flat frequency response between 250 KHz and 500 KHz. They were pre-amplified with a total gain of 60 dB and referred to 5 mV. The threshold voltage was 0.5 V. The thin Teflon film was used to prevent the noise at the contact points.

The response of the specimens were observed through the mechanical tests. The failed specimens were microscopically observed and then tested by ultrasonic method.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The maximum stress of the 8 plied specimens with the ratios of span to the thickness of specimen 40:1 and 16:1 is shown in Fig. 1. The increased shear stress components induced by the small ratio of span to the thickness of specimen have a strong influence on the maximum stress for some structures. The total events of AE are presented to find some relationships with the maximum stress. The total events of

AE show same tendency as the maximum stress variation in off-axis laminates with the ratio of span to the thickness of specimen 40:1. In other cases the total events of AE can not be correlated to the maximum stress. The damage induced by the shear stress and the twisting of the specimens can significantly increase the total events of AE. The fibre breakage itself does not cause significant total events of AE. The crack propagation through the interface between the fibre and the matrix induced less total events of AE than them by matrix cracking. The pronounced delamination causes the most active AE. These results are confirmed by the ultrasonic method and the microscopic observations. In conclusion the complex damage modes with pronounced shear stress c significantly increase the total events of AE.

Figure 1. Variation of Maximum Stress and the Total Events of AE.

The amplitude distribution of AE is useful to represent the internal damage state. The lay-up sequence effect on the peak amplitude distribution in cross-ply laminates is shown in Fig.2. The results show that the matrix cracking and the fibre breakage have lower amplitude than that of delamination. The fibre breakage causes higher amplitude signals than them of matrix crackings.

Figure 2. Lay-up Sequences Effect on the Distribution of Peak Amplitude with the Ratio of Span to the Thickness of Specimen 40:1.

The distribution of peak amplitude with some structures related to the 45° ply is shown in Fig 3. The delamination is important both for the amplitude and the number of events of AE. The amplitude of the AE signals and the number of events of AE are decreased for the structures with the outer layer of 90° ply. This fact illustrates that the matrix cracking is less important than the fibre breakage as the source of AE.

The total events of AE and the distribution of the peak amplitude of AE can be successfully used to determine the various damage and failure modes. But the exact analysis of the AE sources has not well established now. The considerations for the total ring counts down, rate of events, mean peak amplitude per event, distribution of energy, mean rise time of event, duration of the events, the ratio of the energy to the duration of events, the frequency spectrum of AE should be added for the general AE control by using the total events of AE and the distribution of the peak amplitude of AE to determine the various damage and failure mechanisms.

Figure 3. Lay-up Sequences Effect on the Distribution of Peak Amplitude with the Ratio of Span to the Thickness of Specimen 40:1.

CONCLUSION

The matrix cracking and the debonding of phases cause less active AE than the fibre breakage. The delamination produces the most active AE in the respect of total events and the amplitude. The complex damage patterns induced by the presence of shear stress and the lay-up sequences have a very strong influence on the activities of AE. The AE control to determine the failure mode should be accompanied with the supplemental methods for the proper analysis.

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REFERENCES

1. Rosensaft M. and Marom G., J. of Comp. Tech. & Research 7, 1, 1985, pp12-16
2. Falchi A. and Gracia J., "Effects of Three-Point Bending Test Controlled by Acoustic Emission on Carbon Epoxy Laminates", 6th International Conference on Composite Materials, 20-24 July 1987, London, U.K.
3. Kedward, K.T., Fibre Sci. and Tech., 5, 1972, pp85-95
4. Shih G.C. and Ebert L.J., Composites, 17, 4, 1986, pp309-320
5. Robert M.J., J. Comp. Mat., 10, 1976, pp342-354
6. Whitney J.M. and Daukskys R.J., J. Comp. Mat. 4, 1970, pp135-137
7. Nahas M.N., Composites, 6, 2, 1985, pp148-152
8. Marvin A.H., Exp. Mechanics, March. 1986, pp7-13
9. Ohatsu M. and Ono K., J. of Acoustic Emission, 6, 1, 1987, pp61-24
10. Lorenzo L. and Hahn H.T., J. of Acoustic Emission, 5, 1, 1986, pp15-24
11. Shippen N.C. and Adams D.F., J. of Rein. Plas. and Comp. 4, 1985, pp242-161
12. Suzuki M., Nakanishi H., Iwamoto M., Jinen E., Maekawa Z. and Mori A., "Relationship between Acoustic Emission Characteristics and Structural Factors of Composite Materials", in Proceedings of the Third Japan-U.S. Conference on Composite Materials, 23-25 June 1986, Tokyo Japan.
13. Caprino G., Teti R., Mignosi S. and Renta V., "Thickness and Stacking Sequence Effect on the Acoustic Emission of CFRP", Progress in Science and Engineering of Composites, ICCM-IV, Tokyo, Japan, 1982, pp1507-1514
14. Awerbuch J., Block J. and Prinz R., "Effect of Stacking Sequence in Cross-Ply Graphite/Epoxy Laminates on Acoustic Emission Results", Progress in Science and Engineering of Composites, ICCM-IV, Tokyo, Japan, 1982, pp1551-1555